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DELIVERABLE 4.5 – CONCEPT OF VIRTUAL USER INTERFACE (FIRST VERSION)

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Author(s)	Markku Pusenius [CREA], Kaj Helin [VTT], Sebastian Lorenz [TUD]
Contact details of the coordinator	Martijn Rooker, martijn.rooker@tttech.com
Internal Reviewer	Manuel Kulzer [HdM] Anastasia Sergeeva [UL]

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Executive summary

This deliverable is a demonstrator (DEM) presentation. The deliverable presents the concepts of virtual user interfaces and the state of simulation solutions that are developed and used in task *T4.5 Simulation based interaction* in which the goal is to utilize simulation and simulator as a platform to evaluate new user interface solutions. The selected interaction concepts identified in the project are implemented in a simulated environment. The internal states of the simulated models are used to simulate sensor data based on which interaction concepts are controlled.

The focus is on user interactions with the simulated machine operating in a virtual environment. There are dedicated simulators for each of the use case. The UC1 and UC3 simulators are developed by Creanex and both have the capabilities of the Creanex simulator platform. The UC2 simulator is developed by VTT. Game engine graphics are used for visualization and to test XR visualization features. Physics simulation for the work machines of the use cases, snow groomer, reach stacker and excavator, are implemented to enable development, evaluation and testing in virtual environments.

As examples of existing virtualization solutions, a couple of the features of the Creanex simulator platform are presented in section 2. Then an introductory description of the use case simulators is presented in section 3 including description of their main capabilities. Examples of visualization technics and simulation solutions for each use case are presented in section 4 including concept ideas for virtual feedback visualizations.

In the deliverable *D2.2 Technology analysis and requirements specification (first version)* scenarios of the use cases are described including specifications where XR technologies can improve the workflow. The virtual feedback visualizations are based on scenario requirements and identified interaction between the mobile machinery and the human operator. The concepts of the feedback visualizations, which are foreseen to be added to simulations are presented for each use case.

This is the first version of the deliverable *Concept of Virtual User Interface*. The simulated functions and information design of the virtual user interface and simulators are subject to change and will be shaped by the ongoing transdisciplinary co-design process (tasks T3.2 and T3.3). The results of T3.2 will contribute to the development and design of the simulators now that the technological frameworks are in place. The simulations developed for the use cases will also provide a platform to integrate concepts developed in WP3-WP5 into the virtual environment for early testing and demonstration in WP6.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable is a demonstrator presentation and presents the first concepts of virtual user interfaces which simulate the ideas identified as potential new user interface solutions. Implementing ideas first in a simulated environment enables evaluation and discussion of the features in early state and feedback can be collected in safe operating environment. Simulators have the advantage that simulation can be done all year round. Real life tests are vital to understand all aspects of machine operation in changing conditions, but using simulation tools throughout the project is very cost effective compared to arranging test days with real equipment. Simulated user interface solutions also provide opportunities to test ideas which might not yet be feasible to implement in practice but could be enabled by new technologies foreseen.

In task T4.5 simulation and simulators are used to evaluate new user interface solutions. The selected interaction concepts identified in the project will be implemented in a simulated environment and there are dedicated simulators for each of the use cases. The UC1 and UC3 simulators are developed by Creanex and both have the capabilities of the Creanex simulator platform. The UC2 simulator is developed by VTT. Game engine graphics are used for visualization and to test XR visualization features. Physics simulation for the work machines of the use cases, snow groomer, reach stacker and excavator, are implemented to enable development, evaluation and testing in virtual environments.

The user interface of a machine can be divided into control inputs and feedback information. The user interface elements that are common and conventional in present day work machines are shortly presented in section 2.1. Input devices used for controlling a machine are typically joysticks, pedals and switches or push buttons. Feedback information is presented on monitors and by indicators lights for example.

In section 2.2 an example to create virtual counterpart for control panels is presented. Real control panels are not always practical to arrange for all who are using a simulator for different purposes. Virtual panels are software, so they can also be controlled by software to simulate user actions as a test case.

To be able to give feedback, to show more information and to control the machine in a way which considers the non-perceivable state, situational information and measured data are needed. The advantage in simulation is that additional information is available from the model and this information can be used to evaluate extended feedback features cost effectively before trying those with real machines. In section 2.3 an example solution is presented to create configurable sensor signals for machine joints and part positions based on the kinematic structure of a machine.

An introductory description of the use case simulators is presented in section 3 including description of their main capabilities. Examples of visualization technics and simulation solutions for each use case are presented in section 4 including concept ideas for virtual feedback visualizations.

2 Virtual user interface

A virtual user interface is a simulated version of a real one or it can be also a simulated version of a new user interface concept, which is first tested in a virtual environment.

The user interface can be divided into two main parts:

- control interface,
- feedback interface

The operator uses the control devices to give commands to the work machine. The state of the machine and measured sensor data are given as feedback to the operator, see Figure 1.

Figure 1: General structure of user interface.

Section 2.1 summarizes conventional control and feedback devices widely used in work machines. In section 2.2 one existing Creanex Oy solution is described to virtualize conventional control panels. Section 2.3 presents some considerations for virtualizing sensors, including one Creanex implementation, used to measure a state of a machine and to provide feedback for the operator.

2.1 Conventional user interfaces of work machines

Control interfaces may have several different kinds of devices. The most used ones are conventional controls like

- joysticks,
- switches,
- keys,
- push buttons,
- wheels,
- pedals.

New technologies have made it possible to add more sophisticated controls like

- gesture controls based on camera input and
- voice controls with microphone and speech recognition.

Those are not yet common in work machines, but they are getting common in consumer market.

Feedback interface may also be a combination of multiple devices:

- display monitors,
- indicator lights,
- sound speakers.

Some of the user interface devices can be kind of hybrid ones having both control and feedback features:

- touchscreen,
- control joystick with haptic feedback.

Figure 2: Example of a typical user interface in a work machine, case excavator.

2.2 Virtualization of control panels

A control panel can be virtualized on a display monitor as a window having control widgets. This type of virtualization is available on the Creanex simulator platform and can be taken in use in different type of simulator implementations.

Virtualization makes it possible to have the same set of controls in a simulator without any real physical control devices. Of course, having a real cabin or an identical mock-up with all machine controls is authentic operating environment, which has many advantages. If, for example, experienced operators are brought to a simulator, so that they can evaluate and give feedback of the implemented features then it is better to have a similar operating cabin to which they are used to. A realistic simulation can also be controlled by virtual counterparts of real controls on a touch screen. This way the simulator can be cost effectively made available for larger audience and used by different stage holders and project partners.

The virtual user interface panel is available in Creanex simulator platform utilized in use cases 1 and 3. The virtual panel is a window, which can be operated with a mouse or touch screen. The content is configured in a text file having MS INI file format. A user can add named control objects on defined locations of the window. For each control a type is configured and attributes that depend on the selected control type.

For example, a control panel could have a X-Y joystick and a rotary switch. A virtual counterpart would be a window which are two active areas, one for each control. Each active area has a picture which also indicates in which state a control is. In addition, there can be a toolbar to record user actions and to playback recording afterwards.

Figure 3: Example of virtual panel having conventional controls.

The following configuration example shows how the example Figure 3 is configured. First the controls are named in section [UIControls] and then each control is configured in a section named accordingly. The X-Y joystick is named as LeftJoystick, and the two-state rotating switch is named as PowerSwitch.

```
[UIControls]
*Control = LeftJoystick
*Control = BtnStart

[LeftJoystick]
Position = 20 20
Size = 250 250
Name = Crane forward/backward and left/right
Type = JOYSTICK
Image = JoyStickCrosshair.png
Channel1 = IODeviceOfJS LeftJSX
Channel2 = IODeviceOfJS LeftJSY
Horizontal_X = -1024 1023
Horizontal_Y = -100 100
Vertical_X = -1024 1023
Vertical_Y = -100 100

[PowerSwitch]
Position = 20 300
Size = 50 50
Name = PowerSW
Type = BUTTON_ROTARY
RotaryBandStart = 0
RotaryBandRange = 90
PositionCount = 2
Image1 = PowerSwitch-Off.png
Image2 = PowerSwitch-On.png
Staydown = 1 1
Channel1 =
Channel2 = IODeviceOfDashboard PowerSW
```

The graphical object of the joystick showing the active area of the control is JoyStickCrosshair.png set in parameter image, Figure 4. The control position of the joystick is shown by a round dot on top of the background picture, see Figure 3. Joystick position is converted to output value by the Horizontal and Vertical scaling parameters, which define a piecewise line curve by set of value pairs. After scaling the resulting output value is updated to connected IO device defined by Channel parameter.

Figure 4: Background picture for a virtual X-Y joystick.

The number of rotary positions or states a switch can have, is defined by the parameters PositionCount. The PowerSwitch of the example has two states, so two background pictures are defined, Image1 and Image2, shown in Figure 5. Each state has also IO channel and the one of the active state is set on. The parameters RotaryBandStart and RotaryBandRange define sector area to select an active state.

Figure 5: Background pictures for a virtual rotary switch.

There are support for multiple different type of conventional controls used in work machine user interfaces, see table.

Type	Description
BUTTON_PUSH	Push button
BUTTON_HORIZONTAL	Horizontal rocker switch
BUTTON_VERTICAL	Vertical rocker switch
BUTTON_ROTARY	Rotary switch with positions along circumference
BUTTON_ROTARY_ENCODER	Rotary switch having up and down steps in output value
JOYSTICK	Two or single axis joystick
BAR_WIDGET	A bar changing length according to value
VALUE_DISPLAY	Numerical value display

Table 1: Supported control types of virtual panel.

2.3 Virtualization of sensors and feedback

Feedback given for the operator to guide and help him or her to operate the machine is based on measured data of sensors. There are several different type sensors and the most common ones used in work machines are sensors for

- pressure of hydraulic oil or compressed air,
- angle or velocity of a rotary joint,
- position or velocity of a linear joint,
- inclination relative to gravity,
- temperature and
- surrounding clearances around a machine.

A simulated virtual model of a machine has a state based on which the sensors are simulated. For example, parts of a boom are joined together, and a virtual angle sensor is added to measure the angle between the parts, or an inclination sensor is measuring the frame orientation relative to gravity.

Sensor information is often merged into derived information which is then feedback for the operator. Based on kinematic model of a machine and measured joint values the position of the tip of the boom can be calculated and the feedback could be warning if there is a stability risk.

In Creanex simulators the state of the kinematic structure of the machine can be made available as IO channels to simulate sensors. In so called *ObjectStateChannels* configuration it is possible to create simulated sensors for joint values, joint velocity, and position of a selected point on a machine part. First the IO device and the channels are named and then in according to sections the channels are configured to measure selected kinematic attributes of a machine.

```
[IOChannelNames]
IODeviceName = ExcavatorModel
*State = MainBoomAngle
*State = MainBoomVelocity
*State = StickTipPos
```

```
[MainBoomAngle]
Type = MachineJointAngle
Name = MainBoom
```

```
[MainBoomVelocity]
Type = MachineJointVelocity
Name = MainBoom
```

```
[StickTipPos]
Type = MachinePartPosition
Name = Stick
Offset = 2.909 0.0 0.0
Relative = BaseFrame
ShowIndicator = 0
```

Sensor information for surrounding clearances can be simulated by raytracing or depth information from rendered images of a visualization system. The virtual sensor can be an ultrasonic transducer or LIDAR scanner.

Cameras are also very common feedback channel nowadays for example to show rear view or other areas that cannot otherwise been seen from the cabin. Using multiple cameras, a 360-degree top view can be presented for the driver and additional lines and symbols can be added on top of the video for additional information like how a car would turn based on steering.

Figure 6: Camera based parking assistance with AR type of additional helpers.

In a simulated environment it is also possible to simulate video streams. An additional rendering camera can be created in the visual system and rendered images are packed to a video stream.

The geographical location of the operated machine is important feedback information as well. There are many types of systems and devices on the market to measure geographical location. Different manufacturers might have their own proprietary interfaces, but it is very common that location information is available in standard NMEA through a serial or ethernet connection. Creanex simulator supports multiple standard NMEA messages (GGA, RMC, HDT, GSV, GSA, GNS, GMP and VTG [2]) and some manufacturer specific ones of Trimble and Leica (PJK, LLL and LLQ).

Forces acting in parts of a work machine are typically measured from hydraulic cylinder by pressure transducers. Movement simulation is based on available forces, but actual measured forces and pressures come from the counter force from dynamics and environment interactions. In some cases, the load pressure can be well simulated and in some it is more challenging.

Summary of Creanex simulator feedback channels is presented on Figure 7.

Figure 7: Feedback information from Creanex simulators.

3 Simulators and capabilities

Creanex simulator platform is utilized in snow grooming and excavator uses cases 1 and 3. A top level architecture and capabilities of Creanex simulators are presented in section 3.1.

The reachstacker simulator of use case 2 is developed by VTT and it is presented in section 3.2.

3.1 UC1 snow groomer and UC3 excavator simulators and simulator platform capabilities

The main parts of the Creanex simulator structure are

- real or virtualized controls and interfaces for them,
- simulation model, its dynamics and signal interface,
- visualization application,
- visualization media

The Creanex simulator architecture can be divided into layers. At the bottom are the interfaces to external IO devices. The physical controls are typically connected by an IO card or a device having CAN bus interface. Simulator has support for multiple type of IO cards connected by USB and CAN interfaces for CANopen and J1939 nodes. Virtual CAN nodes are also used to simulate for example encoders, inclinometers, pressure transducers and above all a diesel engine. There are also interfaces to external applications. The crnxTesting is interface to Python applications and SimLabLink is interface to MathWorks SimuLink® and Matlab®. One the unique ones is the crnxSoftPLC, which has support for virtual CAN bus and IO channels connected to a virtual counter part of an embedded control unit. Creanex simulator platform contains multi-purpose simulation objects from which the application implementation is derived. The layered structure is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: General architecture of Creanex simulators.

In Creanex simulators the simulation and visualization have separate applications connected by ethernet communication. This has the benefit that there can be multiple visualizations running in separate computers showing a view from different direction or location. Extra visual channel can also be used for generating virtual video streams.

Simulation is series of sub-step that are executed in a loop having fixed time step, typically 20 ms. First the control inputs are measured, and then the raw values are converted to simulation signals, which are further on connected to the simulated machine model. After each simulation step, the new state is sent to the visual application and values of the virtual sensors are updates, see Figure 9. A value of a virtual sensor can be connected to an IO card, CAN message, UDP message and or to the visual to update some augmented visual element.

Figure 9: Creanex simulator applications and IO connection to simulation model.

Creanex simulators have been and are used in many R&D projects. One of the key capabilities is the wide support for control system development and testing. Creanex simulators support both hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) and software-in-the-loop type of simulations (SIL). Creanex technology scales well and there are solutions having only one ECU and some has a dozen ECUs which run code under development and testing. In addition to ECUs there is often many more third-party CAN nodes which are simulated by virtual counterparts.

Simulation is executed in real time. Typically, the IO interface is updated every 10 ms and the dynamic models every 20 ms. Dynamic simulation uses special physics engine which enables interactions with the environment meaning excavator can dig the soil and with a grapple crane one can manipulate objects for example.

Creanex has developed special IO card which can be directly connected to ECU input and output pins. Couple of key features are the electronically simulated feedback current for PWM controls and quadrature encoders.

The virtual control panels and sensors for machine kinematic structure were already presented in sections 2.2 and 2.3. Other capabilities are

- Multiple type of IO cards to connect control panels and ECUs to simulation,
- Configurable signal interface of the simulated models,
- Multi-threaded rigid-body dynamics,
- Support for virtual diesel engine,

- Support for J1939 protocol and virtual nodes based on it,
- Support for CANopen protocol and multiple virtual nodes based CiA device profiles,
- crnxTesting interface for test cases in Python language,
- SimLabLink interface for the Mathworks software products,
- simulated GNSS,
- UDP based IO and signal interface for third party applications,
- Visualization based on Unity game engine.

Creanex simulator platform also supports a motion base. The standard version has two degrees of freedom. The upper frame can tilt around 10 degrees in forward-backwards direction and sideways. Motion of the platform is quite essential in some application like operating an excavator. Having a feeling of the machine movements and inclination increases the realism of the simulation.

Figure 10: Creanex motion platform.

3.2 UC2 reachstacker simulator and its capabilities

The reachstacker simulator is developed by VTT. The application is built using Unity game engine, which supports high quality graphics and built in physics simulation engine.

Figure 11: VTT simulator hardware setup.

The hardware setup (Figure 11) VTT uses for the reachstacker simulation consists of three wall-sized screens, placed with an angle of 120° between each other, Figure 12. The total screen resolution available is 5760x1200 pixels, and the full size of the screens is used to show real-time camera footage from several 360° cameras placed both on the vehicle and on key location of the logistic hub. As input devices, the demo makes use of a Logitech Extreme 3D joystick for controlling the reachstacker's boom and spreader, and an Ultraleap Stereo IR 170 hand-tracking device for controlling the camera views and their position on the screen. A keyboard is also used for handling simulation aspects (such as changing the weather from rain to snow, etc.), and for proving specific commands that were not bound to any of the other peripherals (such as disabling one or both of the AR load charts).

Figure 12: Reachstacker research simulator in VTT simulation environment.

In simulation it is convenient to study different choices for camera views. Currently the test design has four views as shown in Figure 13:

- 1) cabin view/driver's perspective,
- 2) spreader top-down view,
- 3) rear view/counterweight, and
- 4) drone/bird's eye view.

Augmented content is based on several available sensors and other data and the content can be camera view specific.

Figure 13: Reachstacker simulator with four parallel camera views.

The demo intentionally includes a high number of features available to the user, to study which ones are felt to be the most useful and help the operator to do container handling better.

Other capabilities are

- support for the Haption Virtuose 6D haptic control device,
- virtual weight sensor,
- virtual inertial measurement unit,
- weather simulation (wind strength and direction, temperature, humidity),
- virtual LIDAR sensor and
- support for Varjo XR3 headset.

Varjo XR-3 headset supports video pass through technology, which allows users to see the actual remote operation station and virtual representation of the reach stacker and harbour environment all at the same time. A screen capture of the test setup is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Varjo XR3 headset is capable to merge real time video with rendered graphics view.

4 Virtual feedback visualization concepts

In the following sections visualization concepts are presented that are identified for each use case.

4.1 Visualization examples for augmented information

There are several techniques how to add augmented information to rendered 3D graphics. There can be symbols as 3D objects or lines made of piecewise linear 3D tubes. Adding 3D objects like humans can be used to enrich scenarios for collision avoidance test cases.

Laser projector and rotatable spotlight are promising technologies that are foreseen to be used for providing XR content for a work machine operator. Two 3D graphics technics are presented how laser projection and spotlight can be simulated in 3D graphics.

4.1.1 Decal projector

The High-Definition Render Pipeline (HDRP) in Unity includes the Decal Projector component, which allows projection of specific Materials (pictures) into the Scene. When the Decal Projector component projects decals into the Scene, they interact with the Scene's lighting and wrap around Meshes. You can use thousands of decals in your Scene simultaneously. This means that the rendering process is not resource intensive if the decals use the same Material [1].

For example, a bitmap used as the material of a decal is in Figure 15 and the result when the decal projector wraps the material along the ground surface is presented in Figure 16.

Figure 15: Bitmap used in a material.

Figure 16: Decal projector wraps a material on ground surface.

The decal projector can also be used to draw virtual *laser* lines along the ground surface. In Figure 17 two thick lines have been projected on excavated work site.

Figure 17: Projected lines along ground surface.

A decal projector can be used as a virtual equivalent of a laser projector. For example, in UC1 projected decals can highlight the outer borders of previously groomed slope lanes on the ground, so that operators can estimate the right overlap and work more efficiently. In UC3, decals may be used to project the edges of a planned trench on the ground, allowing operators to work precisely even when the original (chalk or spray) markings on the real soil have been torn up or covered by dirt.

4.1.2 Spotlight

A spotlight emits light from a specified location and range over which the light diminishes. The spotlight constrains the light it emits to an angle, which results in a cone-shaped region of illumination. Light may also diminish at the edges of the spotlight's cone. Increasing a spot angle increases the width of the cone.

A spotlight has an emitting location and direction, which can be controlled by simulation. In Figure 18 a spotlight is shown in slightly foggy weather condition, so the cone of the light is also visible. Spotlight may have almost any colour, even black.

Figure 18: Spotlight.

The spotlight can be used in use cases to highlight detected obstacles and/or persons in the vicinity of the work machine.

4.2 Use case 1

4.2.1 Snow groomer simulation

Snow groomer simulation is based on the Creanex simulator platform. Virtual working environment, the simulation scene, has been created from real slope data provided by Prinoth. The LandXml data model was imported to the open-source 3D modelling software Blender¹ and surrounding land scape was built from freely available satellite point-cloud data². The scene can be interpreted to be a digital twin of the real environment, Figure 19.

Figure 19: Snow groomer in simulated working environment.

In Figure 20 the view of the cabin is shown in three different lightning conditions: dusk, night and fog.

Figure 20: Snow groomer cabin view and examples of lightning conditions.

4.2.2 Feedback concepts for snow groomer operator

In deliverable D2.2 three snow groomer scenarios are described including specifications where XR technologies can improve the workflow. The scenarios are

1. build slope matching target surface,
2. obstacle avoidance and
3. zero sight navigation.

The scenarios are divided into tasks and requirements of each task are analysed. Based on the requirements useful feedback concepts have been identified to help the operator to more effectively

- navigate to the target area,
- have clear picture where the vehicle is relative to the target area,

¹ <https://www.blender.org/>

² https://www.opendem.info/opendemeu_download_highres.html

- see progress of the work,
- monitor vehicle path and groom parallel lanes precisely,
- see deviation between the actual and target surfaces,
- avoid obstacles or skiers.

The feedback visualization concepts envisioned in the use case 1, snow groomer, are presented in Figure 21:

- dash lines to indicate snow height,
- shield width lines on both sides to highlight grooming lanes,
- area restriction lines,
- route navigation lines,
- object highlight by a light spot,
- indicator light matrix on side or bottom edges of the cabin to show deviation between actual and target surfaces.

Figure 21: Concept ideas for use case 1 feedback and visualization.

4.3 Use case 2

4.3.1 Reachstacker simulation

The reachstacker simulation is developed by VTT. The simulated scenario is container handling in a harbour area, Figure 22.

Figure 22: Reachstacker in simulated working environment.

The reachstacker can be operated from the cabin of the machine or from a remote station. The simulation supports both, but focus is more on the remote operation using camera views. The operator follows multiple camera streams simultaneously and observes how the container approaches the landing point on e.g., a truck or another stack of containers and how it settles in place.

In simulation the rendering camera showing a view can be freely positioned in the world or mounted on a machine part. One typical camera setup is to mount it inside a cabin looking forward in driving direction and then the camera moves with the machine. The camera can also be programmed to follow an object automatically keeping it in sight. The shown augmented information can be customized to function the way found most useful in different setups.

A setup was created on which user can choose between four different camera views:

- 1) cabin view/driver's perspective with route navigation indication, Figure 23.
- 2) spreader top-down view, Figure 24
- 3) rear view/counterweight and obstacle tracking, Figure 25
- 4) cabin or spreader view with load charts, Figure 26

Figure 23: Reachstacker AR guidance system: vehicle path and pick up/place locations.

Figure 24: Reachstacker AR guidance system: twist lock/corner casting positions, centre line, and tipping axis.

Figure 25: Reachstacker AR guidance system: counterweight safety area and obstacle tracking.

Figure 26: Reachstacker AR guidance system: load charts.

More details of UI concepts, user evaluations and videos are presented in *Deliverable 3.4 – Low-Fidelity XR Prototypes (First Version)*.

4.3.2 Feedback concepts for reachstacker operator

In deliverable D2.2 three reachstacker scenarios are described including specifications where XR technologies can improve the workflow. The scenarios are

1. pick a container from the stack,
2. place a container to the stack,
3. pick a container from ground,
4. place a container on ground,
5. pick a container from the trailer and
6. place a container to the trailer.

The scenarios are divided into tasks and requirements of each task are analysed. Based on the requirements useful feedback concepts have been identified to help the operator to more effectively

- navigate to a container which is ordered to be picked up,
- position the spreader precisely relative to the container and to ensure the container can be grasped safely,
- see that twist locks are locked properly before the container is lifted,
- see that twist locks are fully open when spreader is lifted off the container,
- see that the container is precisely above where it is placed on,
- identify dangerous situations in time like humans in near vicinity or stability risks,
- see the weight distribution of the container,
- avoid collisions.

The feedback visualization concepts envisioned in the use case 2, reachstacker, are presented in Figure 27:

- virtual load chart and container location on it,
- lines for allowable operation area,
- highlight of corner pin positions and weight on them,
- indication of centre of mass
- indication distance to container
- object recognition and highlight,
- route navigation,
- spreader status indication and orientation relative to container.

Figure 27: Concept ideas for use case 2 feedback and visualization.

4.4 Use case 3

4.4.1 Excavator simulation

Excavator simulation is based on Creanex simulator platform. Virtual working environment is an artificial construction site.

Figure 28: Excavator in simulated working environment.

The surface of the earth is simulated in such a way that a hole or a ditch can be excavated.

Figure 29: Excavator cabin view and excavatable soil.

The 3D graphics engine has tools and features to add augmented information on rendered view. For example, outer circumference of an object can be highlighted as shown in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Highlighted object.

4.4.2 Feedback concepts for excavator operator

In deliverable D2.2 three excavator scenarios are described including specifications where XR technologies can improve the workflow. The scenarios are

1. finish grading,
2. collision avoidance and
3. infield design.

The scenarios are divided into tasks and requirements of each task are analysed. Based on the requirements useful feedback concepts have been identified to help the operator to more effectively

- see that the reference height is set correctly,
- assess the alignment between real environment and digital model of the target,
- deviation between the actual and target surfaces,
- plan the work,
- identify dangerous situations in time like humans in near vicinity or stability risks and
- avoid collisions.

The feedback visualization concept envisioned in use case 3, excavator, are presented in Figure 31.

- target depth indication,
- difference to target height,
- work area indication and planning,
- Object detection, warning, and highlighting.

Figure 31: Concept ideas for use case 3 feedback and visualization.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable presents the concept of virtual user interface and how simulators can and are being used in development and testing. Using virtual control panels, the simulator is cost effectively taken in use without first investing on hardware platform. To be able to show more information new sensors and environment data models are needed based on which new information is derived and made visible. In simulated environment the data exist in the model and can be made available for systems under development.

The 3D graphics technics decal projection and spotlight can be used to simulate augmented visual effects that have foreseen to be tested in the THEIA^{XR} project. Decal projection can be used to add symbols and lines on terrain surface. Spotlight can have different colours and used to highlight objects. The current states of the simulators used in the use cases are presented. The simulators of the use cases are under development and screen captures are included to show current states.

In the deliverable *D2.2 Technology analysis and requirements specification (first version)* scenarios are described including specifications where XR technologies can improve the workflow. The scenarios are divided into tasks and based on analysed requirements feedback concepts have been identified to help the operator to do the work more effectively and safely. The concepts of the feedback visualizations, which are foreseen to be added to simulations were presented for each use case.

The focus is on user interactions with the simulated machine operating in a virtual environment. The simulated functions and information design of the virtual user interface and simulators are subject to change and will be shaped by the ongoing transdisciplinary co-design process (tasks T3.2 and T3.3), where planned features and information elements are scrutinized, co-designed and validated in collaboration with vehicle operators. The results of T3.2, which is currently in the stage of validating concepts for features in UC1 and UC3, will now increasingly contribute to the development and design of the simulators now that the technological frameworks are in place. The virtual environments and simulations together with the cabin mockup presented in the deliverable *D5.5 Multimodal immersive cockpit* are envisioned to allow evaluation and prototyping of simulated feedback modalities beyond the cabin environment. The simulations developed for the use cases will also provide a platform to integrate concepts developed in WP3-WP5 into the virtual environment for early testing and demonstration.

References

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

AR	Augmented Reality
CAN	Controller Area Network
CiA	CAN in Automation
ECU	Embedded Control Unit
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HDM	Head-mounted Display
HIL	Hardware in the loop
NMEA	National Marine Electronics Association
PWM	Pulse width modulated
SIL	Software in the loop
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	eXtended Reality